

Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ - Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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ABSTRACT

Aim of this present paper is, we introduce and investigate a new class of closed sets is called Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces and its properties and characterization are discussed details.

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1. INTRODUCTION

C.L. Chang³ was introduced and developed fuzzy topological space by using L.A. Zadeh's¹⁴ fuzzy sets. Coker⁴ introduced the notion of Intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces by using Atanassov's¹ Intuitionistic fuzzy set. Neutrality the degree of indeterminacy, as an independent concept, was introduced by Smarandache⁷ in 1998. He also defined the Neutrosophic set on three component Neutrosophic topological spaces $(t, f, i) = (\text{Truth, Falsehood, Indeterminacy})$, The Neutrosophic crisp set concept was converted to Neutrosophic topological spaces by A. A. Salama¹⁰. I. Arokiarani.² *et al.*, introduced Neutrosophic α -closed sets. Santhi. R¹¹ *et al.*, introduced and studied about Neutrosophic ω -closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces. Aim of this present paper is, we introduce and investigate a new class of closed sets is called Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces and its properties and characterization are discussed details

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we introduce the basic definition for Neutrosophic sets and its operations.

Definition 2.1 [7]

Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A Neutrosophic set A is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Where $\mu_A(x)$, $\sigma_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ which represent Neutrosophic topological spaces the degree of membership function, the degree indeterminacy and the degree of non-membership function respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

Remark 2.2 [7]

A Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ can be identified to an ordered triple $\langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle$ in $\alpha-0, 1+\alpha$ on X .

Remark 2.3[7]

we shall use the symbol

$$A = \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle \text{ for the Neutrosophic set } A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}.$$

Example 2.4 [7]

Every Neutrosophic set A is a non-empty set in X is obviously on Neutrosophic set having the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), 1 - (\mu_A(x) + \gamma_A(x)), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$. Since our main purpose is to construct the tools for developing Neutrosophic set and Neutrosophic topology, we must introduce the Neutrosophic set 0_N and 1_N in X as follows:

0_N may be defined as:

$$(0_1) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_2) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_3) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(0_4) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

1_N may be defined as :

$$(1_1) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_2) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_3) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$(1_4) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 1, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Definition 2.5 [7]

Let $A = \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle$ be a Neutrosophic set on X , then the complement of the set A

A^C defined as

$$A^C = \{ \langle x, \gamma_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Definition 2.6 [7]

Let X be a non-empty set, and Neutrosophic sets A and B in the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \text{ and}$$

$$B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}.$$

Then we consider definition for subsets ($A \subseteq B$).

$A \subseteq B$ defined as: $A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_B(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x)$ for all $x \in X$

Proposition 2.7 [7]

For any Neutrosophic set A, then the following condition are holds:

- (i) $0_N \subseteq A, 0_N \subseteq 0_N$
- (ii) $A \subseteq 1_N, 1_N \subseteq 1_N$

Definition 2.8 [7]

Let X be a non-empty set, and $A = \langle X, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle$, $B = \langle X, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle$ be two Neutrosophic sets. Then

- (i) $A \cap B$ defined as : $A \cap B = \langle X, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$
- (ii) $A \cup B$ defined as : $A \cup B = \langle X, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_B(x) \rangle$

Definition 2.9 [7]

We can easily generalize the operation of intersection and union in Definition 2.8 to arbitrary family of Neutrosophic sets as follows:

Let $\{ A_j : j \in J \}$ be an arbitrary family of Neutrosophic sets in X, then

- (i) $\cap A_j$ defined as :
 $\cap A_j = \langle X, \bigwedge_{j \in J} \mu_{A_j}(x), \bigwedge_{j \in J} \sigma_{A_j}(x), \bigvee_{j \in J} \gamma_{A_j}(x) \rangle$
- (ii) $\cup A_j$ defined as :
 $\cup A_j = \langle X, \bigvee_{j \in J} \mu_{A_j}(x), \bigvee_{j \in J} \sigma_{A_j}(x), \bigwedge_{j \in J} \gamma_{A_j}(x) \rangle$

Proposition 2.10 [9]

For all A and B are two Neutrosophic sets then the following condition are true:

- (1) $(A \cap B)^c = A^c \cup B^c$
- (2) $(A \cup B)^c = A^c \cap B^c$.

Definition 2.11 [10]

A Neutrosophic topology is a non -empty set X is a family τ_N of Neutrosophic subsets in X satisfying the following axioms:

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$,
- (ii) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau_N$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in \tau_N$,
- (iii) $\cup G_i \in \tau_N$ for every $G_i \in \tau_N, i \in J$.

the pair (X, τ_N) is called a Neutrosophic topological space.

The element Neutrosophic topological spaces of τ_N are called Neutrosophic open sets.

A Neutrosophic set A is closed if and only if A^c is Neutrosophic open.

Example 2.12[10]

Let $X = \{x\}$ and

$$A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.6, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_3 = \{ \langle x, 0.6, 0.7, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_4 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.6, 0.9 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Then the family $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ is called a Neutrosophic topological space on X.

Definition 2.13[10]

Let (X, τ_N) be Neutrosophic topological spaces and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ be a Neutrosophic set in X . Then the Neutrosophic closure and Neutrosophic interior of A are defined by

$$\text{Neu-cl}(A) = \bigcap \{ K : K \text{ is a Neutrosophic closed set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K \}$$

$$\text{Neu-int}(A) = \bigcup \{ G : G \text{ is a Neutrosophic open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}.$$

Definition 2.14[10]

(i) A is Neutrosophic open set if and only if $A = \text{Neu-int}(A)$.

(ii) A is Neutrosophic closed set if and only if $A = \text{Neu-cl}(A)$.

Proposition 2.15[10]

For any Neutrosophic set A in (X, τ_N) we have

(i) $\text{Neu-cl}((A^c)) = (\text{Neu-int}(A))^c$,

(ii) $\text{Neu-int}((A^c)) = (\text{Neu-cl}(A))^c$.

Proposition 2.16[10]

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological spaces and A, B be two Neutrosophic sets in X . Then the following properties are holds:

- (i) $\text{Neu-int}(A) \subseteq A$,
- (ii) $A \subseteq \text{Neu-cl}(A)$,
- (iii) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \text{Neu-int}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-int}(B)$,
- (iv) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \text{Neu-cl}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-cl}(B)$,
- (v) $\text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-int}(A)) = \text{Neu-int}(A)$,
- (vi) $\text{Neu-cl}(\text{Neu-cl}(A)) = \text{Neu-cl}(A)$,
- (vii) $\text{Neu-int}(A \cap B) = \text{Neu-int}(A) \cap \text{Neu-int}(B)$,
- (viii) $\text{Neu-cl}(A \cup B) = \text{Neu-cl}(A) \cup \text{Neu-cl}(B)$,
- (ix) $\text{Neu-int}(0_N) = 0_N$,
- (x) $\text{Neu-int}(1_N) = 1_N$,
- (xi) $\text{Neu-cl}(0_N) = 0_N$,
- (xii) $\text{Neu-cl}(1_N) = 1_N$,
- (xiii) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow B^c \subseteq A^c$,
- (xiv) $\text{Neu-cl}(A \cap B) \subseteq \text{Neu-cl}(A) \cap \text{Neu-cl}(B)$,
- (xv) $\text{Neu-int}(A \cup B) \supseteq \text{Neu-int}(A) \cup \text{Neu-int}(B)$.

Definition: 2.17[8]

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological space. Then A is called Neutrosophic semi-open if $A \subseteq \text{Neu-cl}(\text{Neu-int}(A))$.

The complement of Neutrosophic semi-open set is called Neutrosophic semi-closed.

Definition: 2.18[10]

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological space Then A is called Neutrosophic α -open set if $A \subseteq \text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-cl}(\text{Neu-int}(A)))$.

The complement of Neutrosophic α -open set is called Neutrosophic α -closed.

Definition 2.19 [5]

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological space. Then A is called generalized Neutrosophic closed (Neu g -closed) if $\text{Neu-cl}(A) \subseteq U$, whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is Neu-open set. The complement of a Neu g -closed set is called the Neu g -open sets.

Definition 2.20 [11]

Let (X, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological space. Then A is called Neutrosophic ω -closed set (Neu ω -closed set for short) if $\text{Neu-cl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is Neu semi-open set.

Remark:2.21[11]

Let A be an Neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) . Then

- (i) $\text{Neu}\alpha\text{-cl}(A) = A \cup \text{Neu-cl}(\text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-cl}(A)))$.
- (ii) $\text{Neu}\alpha\text{-int}(A) = A \cap \text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-cl}(\text{Neu-int}(A)))$.

3. NEUTROSOPHIC $\omega\alpha$ -CLOSED SETS

In this section, we introduce the concept of Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed sets (Shortly Neu $\omega\alpha$ - closed set) and some of their properties are discussed details. Throughout this paper (X, τ_N) represent a Neutrosophic topological spaces.

Definition 3.1

A subset A of a Neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is said to be Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set if $\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is Neu ω -open in (X, τ_N) .

The complement of Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed sets is called Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -open sets

Example 3.2:

Let $X = \{x\}$. $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A_1\}$ be a Neutrosophic topological space where $A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.3, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$.

$S = \{ \langle x, t_1, t_2, t_3 \rangle : x \in X, t_1 \in [0.3, 1), t_2 \in [0.6, 1) \text{ and } t_3 \in (0, 0.5] \}$.

Neutrosophic semi open set is $\{0_N, 1_N, A_1, S\}$

Neutrosophic α -open set is $\{0_N, 1_N, A_1, S\}$

Neutrosophic ω -open set is $\{0_N, 1_N, A_1\}$.

Here $A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.3:

Every Neutrosophic closed set is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set.

Proof:

Let A be Neutrosophic closed set in a Neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) . Let G be any Neutrosophic ω - open set in (X, τ_N) such that $A \subseteq G$. Since A is closed we have, $\text{Neu-cl}(A) = A$. But $\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-cl}(A)$ is always true, so $\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq \text{Neu-cl}(A) \subseteq G$. Therefore $\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq G$. Hence A is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set in (X, τ_N) .

The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example: 3.4

From the Example.3.2, Here we consider $A = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.8, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ which is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set but not Neutrosophic closed set.

Theorem 3.5:

Every Neutrosophic α -closed set is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set.

Proof:

Let A be Neutrosophic α -closed set in a Neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) . Let G be any Neutrosophic ω -open set in (X, τ_N) such that $A \subseteq G$. Since A is Neutrosophic α -closed set, we have, $\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A) = A$. Therefore $\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subseteq G$. Hence A is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set in (X, τ_N) .

The converse of the above theorem need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 3.6

From the Example.3.2, Here we consider $B = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.8, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ which is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set but not Neutrosophic α -closed set.

Remark:3.7

Neutrosophic g - closed, Neutrosophic ω - closed and Neutrosophic-semi closed are independent of Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set.

Example 3.8

Let $X = \{x\}$. $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A_1, A_2\}$ be a Neutrosophic topological space

Where $A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ $A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$.

Here we consider $C = \{ \langle x, 0.3, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ which is Neutrosophic g -closed but not Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set.

Example 3.9

Let $X = \{x\}$. $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A_1, A_2\}$ be a Neutrosophic topological space

Where $A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.3, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$

Here we consider $D = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.2, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$ Which is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed but not Neutrosophic g - closed.

Example 3.10

Let $X = \{x\}$. $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A_1, A_2\}$ be a Neutrosophic topological space. Where

$A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ $A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$

Here we consider $G = \{ \langle x, 0.3, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ which is Neutrosophic ω -closed but not Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set.

Example 3.10

Let $X = \{x\}$. $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A_1, A_2\}$ be a Neutrosophic topological space

where $A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.3, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$, $A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$,

Here we consider $H = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.8, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ which is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed but not Neutrosophic ω -closed.

Example 3.11

Let $X=\{x\}$. $\tau_N=\{0_N, 1_N, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ be a Neutrosophic topological space

$$A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.3, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.2, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_3 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.6, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

$$A_4 = \{ \langle x, 0.3, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Here we consider $I = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.2, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$ which is Neutrosophic semi-closed but not Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed set.

Example 3.12

Let $X=\{x\}$. $\tau_N=\{0_N, 1_N, A_1, A_2\}$ be a Neutrosophic topological space

Where $A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.3, 0.6, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$,

$$A_2 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Here we consider $F = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.8, 0.5 \rangle, \langle x, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$ which is Neutrosophic $\omega\alpha$ -closed but not Neutrosophic semi closed.

Neu ω -closed

Diagram-I

Where $A \rightarrow B$ represents A implies B but B does not implies A

Where $A \leftrightarrow B$ represents A independent B each other.

4. PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERIZATION OF NEU $\omega\alpha$ -CLOSED SETS

Theorem 4.1

The finite union of Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed sets is Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed.

Proof:

Let A and B be two Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed subsets of a space (X, τ_N) .

Then for each Neu ω -open Set U and V in (X, τ_N) containing A and B such that $Neu \alpha-cl(A) \subseteq U$ and $Neu \alpha-cl(B) \subseteq V$ respectively. Hence $A \cup B \subseteq U \cup V$. Since arbitrary union of Neu ω -open sets in (X, τ_N) is also Neu ω -open Set in (X, τ_N) , $U \cup V$ is Neu ω -open in (X, τ_N) . Also $Neu \alpha-cl(A \cup B) = Neu \alpha-cl(A) \cup Neu \alpha-cl(B) \subseteq U \cup V$. Therefore $A \cup B$ is Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed in (X, τ_N) .

Remark 4.2:

Intersection of any two Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed sets in (X, τ_N) need not be Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed. Let $X = \{x\}$ and $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A_1\}$ be a Neutrosophic topological space, from the Example 3.2. Here we consider two subsets $A_6 = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.8, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $A_5 = \{ \langle x, 0.5, 0.7, 0.4 \rangle : x \in X \}$ are Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed sets but their intersection of two sets $A_1 = \{ \langle x, 0.4, 0.7, 0.5 \rangle : x \in X \}$, is not Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed.

Theorem 4.3

Prove that any non-empty Neu ω -closed set does not contain both Neu α -cl(A) and A^C . Where A is Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed set of (X, τ_N) .

Proof:

Assume that A is Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed. Assume that contrary, Let G be non-empty Neu ω -closed set contained in Neu α -cl(A) and A^C . Now G^C is Neu ω -open set of (X, τ_N) such that $A \subseteq G^C$. Here A is Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed Set of (X, τ_N) . Thus Neu α -cl(A) $\subseteq G^C$. Therefore $G \subseteq$ Neu α -cl(A) $\subseteq G^C$.

we get $\mu_G(x) \leq \mu_{\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A)}(x)$ and $\gamma_G(x) \geq \gamma_{\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A)}(x)$ for all $x \in X$. and $\mu_{\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A)}(x) \leq \mu_{G^C}(x)$, and $\gamma_{\text{Neu } \alpha\text{-cl}(A)}(x) \geq \gamma_{G^C}(x)$, for all $x \in X$. which is contradiction because $\gamma_G(x) = \mu_{G^C}(x)$, Hence non empty Neu ω -closed set does not contain both Neu α -cl(A) and A^C .

Theorem 4.4

If A is Neu ω -open and Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed subset of (X, τ_N) then A is Neu α -closed subset of (X, τ_N) .

Proof:

We know that $A \subseteq$ Neu α -cl(A). Here A is Neu ω -open and Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed, it implies that Neu α -cl(A) $\subseteq A$. Hence A is Neu α -closed.

Theorem 4.5

The intersection of a Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed set and a Neu ω -closed set is Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed.

Proof:

Let A be Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed and Let G be Neu ω -closed. Take U is a Neu ω -open set with $A \cap G \subseteq U$. This implies $A \subseteq U \cup G^C$. Here $U \cup G^C$ is Neu ω -open set. Therefore Neu α -cl(A) $\subseteq U \cup G^C$. Now Neu α -cl(A) $\cap G \subseteq$ Neu α -cl(A) \cap Neu α -cl(G) = Neu α -cl(A) $\cap G \subseteq (U \cup G^C) \cap G = U$. Here $A \cap G$ is Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed.

Theorem: 4.6

If A is a Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed set in space (X, τ_N) and $A \subseteq B \subseteq$ Neu α -cl(A), then B is also Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed set.

Proof:

Let U be a Neu ω -open set of (X, τ_N) such that $B \subseteq U$. Then $A \subseteq U$. Since A is Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed set, Neu α -cl(A) $\subseteq U$. Also Since $B \subseteq$ Neu α -cl(A), Neu α -cl(B) \subseteq Neu α -cl(Neu α -cl(A)) = Neu α -cl(A). Hence Neu α -cl(B) $\subseteq U$. Therefore B is also a Neu $\omega\alpha$ -closed set.

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